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CFD wind farm evaluation in complex terrain under free and wake induced flow conditions

David Bretos¹, Guillén Campaña-Alonso¹, Beatriz Méndez-López¹,
Elena Cantero-Nouqueret¹

¹National Renewable Energy Center (CENER), Sarriguren, 31621, Spain.

E-mail: dbretos@cener.com

Abstract.

Massive deployment of wind energy is critical to achieving the renewable energy production targets. This requires the development and improvement of models and tools for the optimal exploitation of high altitude and complex terrain sites for wind energy installations. Predicting the wind resource assessment of these sites is very challenging, as is predicting the interaction of wind farms in complex terrain with neighbouring installations, which is necessary to maximise the efficiency of wind energy. To address these challenges, the use of high-fidelity Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) models is recommended. In this study, the wind resource at the complex terrain site of the CENER experimental wind farm (Alaiz) is evaluated using steady-state RANS CFD simulations performed with OpenFOAM v2212, taking into account the effects of terrain topography and vegetation. Furthermore, a virtual wind farm located at Alaiz is modelled with the Actuator Disk (AD) method to analyse the effect of topography on the the wake evolution.

1. Introduction

Microscale wind resource assessment (WRA) in complex terrain (CT) is crucial for identifying suitable sites for wind farms (WF). Mesoscale, analytical and linearised flow models struggle with terrain complexity, leading to higher fidelity approaches such as CFD for microscale modelling. Wind turbine (WT) wakes, downstream regions of reduced wind speed and increased turbulence, significantly affect the performance of downstream turbines, resulting in reduced energy production and increased structural loads. Wakes and CT interaction is influenced by factors such as topography, atmospheric stability, and WT characteristics.

Understanding the wake-topography interaction is critical for WF operators during site planning. Studies such as the Perdigao case in Portugal have extensively instrumented sites to understand flow behaviour under WT wakes, providing valuable data for model development and validation. The wake behaviour under different atmospheric stability conditions was studied at this site using LiDAR technology [1], showing local peaks in the velocity deficit profiles of 70 % at 1D (rotor diameter), and decreasing to 50 % at 3D under neutral conditions. This study concluded that wake propagation is highly complex and strongly dependent on terrain orography and the stability conditions.

This work investigates the wind resource at the CT site of the Alaiz experimental WF, first without the influence of the WF, and then modelling theoretical WTs using the Actuator Disk (AD) method. This work provides a better understanding of the wind flow in CT sites, and it's behaviour with the wake of wind turbines wake.

2. Methodology

This study analyses the highly complex topography of the Alaiz experimental WF. Alaiz is located in a high altitude (elevation 1,100 m) CT 15 km SE from Pamplona (Navarre, Spain). The size of the farm is 30 km x 30 km, and is suitable for the study of high-resolution mesoscale-to-microscale models with strong coupling between terrain and thermal stratification [2]. The prevailing wind directions are from the north and from the south. To the north of the WF there is a large valley at an elevation of around 700m. To the south, the terrain is complex with the presence of some WFs; the closest one is situated 2 km south. The WF has four reference met masts (MP1, MP3, MP5 and MP6) 118 m tall, situated at the north of six wind turbine positions (A1 to A6).

The Alaiz experimental WF site was simulated using OpenFOAM v2212 CFD Finite Volume Method (FVM) code. The vegetation effect was modelled using the aerodynamic roughness height (z_0). Neutral atmospheric stability was modelled using a logarithmic inlet wind profile and including the Coriolis force. The WTs of the WF were modelled with the AD method. The $k - \varepsilon - f_P$ eddy viscosity model (EVM) [3] was used to avoid the wind speed deficits underestimation of the original $k - \varepsilon$ EVM when considering ADs. Experimental data representing neutral atmospheric conditions was used to validate the model. Finally, the influence of a virtual WF with NREL5MW WTs [4] located in the Alaiz experimental WF available positions was studied.

The following steps were taken in this study:

- (i) Mesh sensitivity study of a single AD.
- (ii) Mesh sensitivity study of the CT case.
- (iii) Comparison of $k - \varepsilon$ and $k - \varepsilon - f_P$ EVMs in a highly CT case.
- (iv) Highly CT simulation.
- (v) Highly CT simulation with a virtual WF consisting of 6 WTs.

2.1. Topography - Geometry

The Alaiz experimental WF site has a highly complex topography (Figure 1 (left)). In order to study and model the effect of topography on wind flow, it is necessary to characterise the complexity of the terrain. High-resolution geometry and a subsequent high-resolution mesh for the computations are required. Furthermore, the characterisation of the vegetation diversity (Figure 1 (right)) by means of aerodynamic roughness height [5, 6] is considered.

The high resolution geometry is generated from a high resolution Digital Terrain Model (DTM) obtained from LiDAR flights with a resolution of 2 m. The extent of the modelled terrain is 20 km by 20 km, with the WF located in the centre of the domain.

2.2. Met Masts - Wind Turbines

The available experimental data used to calibrate the model corresponds to a period prior to the installation of the WF. The maximum instrumented height is 118 m above ground level (AGL). During this period there were two different types of met masts: the permanent met masts (MP) and the calibration met masts (MC). The MC met masts were located where the WTs would be installed. The MP met masts are still in place. The locations of the met masts can be seen in Figure 2.

For this study, the data from the met masts MP1, MP3, MP5, MC1, MC2 and MC3 was available. The available data from these met masts concern wind speed and direction at four different heights (118 m, 102 m, 90 m and 78 m AGL) instrumented with wind vanes and cup anemometers.

Figure 1: Map of the Alaiz experimental WF (black rectangle) site in elevation above sea level (a.s.l.) (40 km x 40 km) (left). Potential vegetation zones modelled using aerodynamic roughness heights (20 km x 20 km) (right).

Figure 2: Alaiz experimental WF layout (ETRS89-UTM30N coordinate reference system).

2.3. Simulation Setup

A Reynolds-averaged-Navier-Stokes (RANS) approach was used for all the simulations. Incompressible steady-state simulations were performed using the Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure-Linked Equations-Consistent (SIMPLEC) algorithm [7]. Second order linear-upwind schemes were used for both the momentum and turbulence equations.

The $k - \varepsilon - f_P$ EVM with a variable C_{mu} value, influenced by the tuning constant C_r , is used in the calculations. Previous studies have shown that the conventional $k - \varepsilon$ eddy viscosity model (EVM) tends to underestimate velocity deficits when simulating wind turbine wakes with ADs, while the $k - \varepsilon - f_P$ EVM provides more accurate estimates. In [3], the C_r value of this EVM was tuned to 4.5 using Large Eddy Simulations (LES) for the NREL5MW WT, which is also used in this study for consistency.

The following linear system solvers were used for the equations involving the physics under consideration:

- Pressure equation: The *Geometric-Algebraic Multi-Grid (GAMG)* solver was used to solve the pressure equation. The *DICGaussSeidel* smoother was used for a faster convergence. A tolerance of $1e-14$ and a relative tolerance of 0.01 was set. A V-cycle with 3 post-sweeps and the *faceAreaPair* coarsening/agglomeration algorithm was used.

- Momentum and turbulence equations: the *smoothSolver* solver with the *symGaussSeidel* smoother was used. A tolerance of 1e-14 and a relative tolerance of 0.01 was set.

To deal with the non-orthogonal cells due to the highly complex topography of the site, 3 *nNonOrthogonalCorrectors* were used to ensure the convergence of the simulations. A residual control of 1e-6 was set up for all the equations after studying the effect of this choice on the variables of interest (wind speed at hub height).

2.4. Neutral Atmospheric Stability

Neutral atmospheric conditions were considered for these simulations, thermal phenomena were not considered. The neutral atmospheric stability was modelled by the idealised logarithmic wind profile. A turbulence intensity of 10 % was considered.

The Coriolis force was also taken into account using a source term assigned to all cells in the computational domain to account for the horizontal and vertical components of the Coriolis force induced by the Earth's rotation. A planetary rotation period of 23.934 *h/day* and a latitude of 42.7° (according to the WF location) were assigned to set up the source term, resulting in a Coriolis parameter of $0.729 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

The inclusion of the Coriolis source term with an idealised logarithmic wind profile showed a good agreement with the experimental data in the CT site of Perdigao [8].

2.5. Wind Turbines Modelling

The WTs are modelled using the AD method with a variable scaling approach [9]. This approach makes it possible to perform a dynamic calibration of the WF when there are several WTs downstream. This is not the case in this study, but in order to improve the study of the WF wake effect on other WFs in the vicinity in future work, this AD method has been chosen.

2.6. Experimental - Validation Data

The experimental data used for model calibration and validation covers the period prior to the installation of the WTs, from August to December 2010. Only one wind speed and direction (north) is simulated.

With no sonic anemometers or ground temperature data available, the Monin-Obukhov length [10] calculation isn't feasible. Simplified methods such as Pasquill-Gifford classification [11] result in significant data loss when synchronising towers. Therefore, the available data from both the north and south wind directions are split and the average wind speed and direction for the north direction is calculated, assuming neutral atmospheric conditions. An uncertainty of 3.2 % is estimated in the procedures for obtaining wind speed measurements [12].

3. Simulations

Mesh sensitivity studies for AD and CT are performed, followed by a comparison between the $k - \varepsilon$ and $k - \varepsilon - f_P$ EVMs in CT conditions without considering wakes. Subsequently, the CT model is calibrated and validated using experimental data before finally modelling the WTs wakes in the CT.

3.1. Actuator Disk Mesh Sensitivity Study

Although mesh sensitivity studies have been carried out in previous studies [3], this study investigates the mesh requirements when considering the $k - \varepsilon - f_P$ EVM with a WT modelled by the AD method due to the use of a different meshing strategy (unstructured meshes).

Figure 3 shows the mesh refinement region (RR). The mesh background is defined as a function of the rotor diameter (D) of the NREL5MW WT [4]. Three different background sizes are studied, maintaining a refinement ratio (r) of 2 (Table 1). The RR has a refinement level of

2, 10 surface layers are used with a constant expansion ratio of 1.12. The Global Convergence Index (GCI) method [13] with a safety factor (F_s) of 1.25 is used for this study .

Figure 3: AD mesh characteristics depending on rotor diameter (D). AD selected cells in red.

Table 1: AD mesh characteristics.

Mesh	Background size	1st layer size [m]	Cells/D	N. Cells
A	0.500 D	1	8	208,477
B	0.250 D	2	16	1,437,401
C	0.125 D	4	32	10,660,139

The GCI calculation involves adimensionalising the wind speed integrated over the rotor area with the freestream speed integrated over the rotor area at various wake D distances. Mesh B has a GCI below 0.6 % while Mesh C has a GCI below 0.2 %. In [3] it is recommended to use at least 8 cells per rotor diameter in the AD area when using $k - \epsilon - f_P$ EVM with structured meshes, but it shows small deviations from the two other finer meshes studied with 16 and 32 cells per rotor diameter in the AD area. After carrying out this study with unstructured meshes and seeing some common conclusions with the work of other authors, the features of mesh B (16 cells per rotor diameter) were selected for the subsequent WF simulations due to its balanced GCI/cell number ratio and agreement with the finest mesh.

3.2. Complex Terrain Mesh Sensitivity Study

A mesh refinement study based on the GCI method was carried out to define the CT mesh features. Two RRs are considered (Figure 4), RR1 (refinement level 2) and RR2 (refinement level 3); focusing on the area of interest (the WF site). Additionally, a surface refinement level of 3 is applied to the topography surface.

The mesh background size is defined according to D (Table 2), 10 surface layers with a constant expansion ratio of 1.12 and a constant first layer thickness of 4 m are used. The first surface layer thickness is different from that defined for mesh B in the AD mesh sensitivity study in Section 3.1, as aerodynamic roughness heights up to 2 m are going to be considered.

Three meshes are studied keeping a refinement ratio (r) of 2. The hub height wind speed at met masts MC1, MC2 and MC3 is considered for this study. The GCI for mesh C is less than 2.72 % for all the met masts studied, these mesh features are selected for the calculations.

Figure 4: Terrain mesh characteristics. General overview (left) and zoom at WF location (right).

Table 2: CT mesh characteristics.

Mesh	Background	N. Cells	$U_{H,MC1}$ [m/s]	$U_{H,MC2}$ [m/s]	$U_{H,MC3}$ [m/s]
A	4 D	991,347	13.089	13.239	12.741
B	2 D	3,968,840	12.675	12.644	12.118
C	1 D	16,718,041	12.608	12.5882	12.012

3.3. $k - \varepsilon$ and $k - \varepsilon - f_P$ EVMs Comparison in Highly Complex Terrain

The $k - \varepsilon - f_P$ EVM is a variable C_{mu} EVM based on the $k - \varepsilon$ EVM. This modified EVM is used in the modelling of WTs by ADs in order to better predict the velocity deficit in the WT wakes. However, the use of this EVM instead of the constant C_{mu} EVM could question its suitability for cases where WTs are not modelled by ADs. Both EVMs were compared and showed a good agreement (Figure 5) in wind speed (U), turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) and wind direction for the different met masts, leading to the selection of the $k - \varepsilon - f_P$ EVM for all the simulations.

Figure 5: $k - \varepsilon$ and $k - \varepsilon - f_P$ EVMs comparison at met mast MP1 site. The radius of the polar plot (right) refers to the height AGL.

3.4. Complex Terrain Model Validation

The CT model was calibrated to match the experimental data in terms of wind speed and direction and to validate its suitability for the subsequent simulation.

Six met masts were used to validate the model: MP1, MP3, MP5, MC1, MC2 and MC3. For all the met masts except for the MP5, the estimated wind speed is within the experimental

uncertainty range. The maximum wind speed deviation from experimental data occurs at the MP5 met mast at 102 m AGL with an overestimation of 0.768 m/s, while the maximum wind direction deviation is of 12.02° and occurs at the MP1 met mast at 78 m AGL (Figure 6). The turbulence intensity value at hub height is around 10 % for all the met masts locations.

Figure 6: Evolution of wind speed and direction with height (up to 120 m) at met masts site; and experimental data (black dots with error bars). The radius of the polar plots refers to the height AGL.

Figure 7: Wind speed components of the met masts.

In Figure 7 the met masts at WTs positions (MCs) show a high U_x component (western direction). The met masts at westerly positions show a higher westerly wind component due to the flow acceleration in that direction (270°) caused by a topographic depression to the west of

the WF (Figure 8). The further east the WT is located, the less the met masts are affected by this topographic feature.

Figure 8: Flow streamlines in the WF vicinity.

3.5. Complex Terrain with Wind Farm Influence

In this phase, the CT model incorporates the Alaiz WF influence by positioning the virtual NREL 5MW WT in each of its six available locations. The AD mesh strategy defined in Section 3.1 is applied within the context of the CT mesh strategy defined in Section 3.2.

The calibrated model wind speeds at hub height at the MCs locations (Section 3.4) are used to define the C_p and C_T for the modelled WTs in the WF simulations.

The results are presented in the direction of the free stream velocity (north to south) as a function of a dimensionless distance (D^*). These dimensionless coordinates are associated with the x_{UTM30N} values in terms of D distances from the position of WT1 (MC1), which is the southernmost located WT.

Figure 9: Normalised absolute velocity along x_{UTM30N} coordinates AGL for the CT without (CT) and with (CT+WF) WF at hub height.

The CT wake is compared with and without the influence of the WF layout. Figure 9 shows the natural wake speed deficit of the CT at hub height (90 m AGL). The contribution of each WT to the natural wake of the terrain can be seen at $2.5D^*$ (wind speed deficits up to 29.46 %). At $5D^*$ it is no longer possible to distinguish the contribution of WT5 and WT6 to the global wake in CT (wind speed deficits up to 18.53 %). At $10D^*$ the contribution of each WT is not noticeable and a generalised wind speed deficit appears. At $20D^*$, $25D^*$ and $50D^*$ it is no

longer possible to distinguish the contribution of each WT to the global wake. At $75D^*$ (9450 m), there is a complete recovery of the wake in the transects concerning the WT1, WT4, WT5 and WT6. While there is still a noticeable wind speed deficit in the transects concerning the WT2 and WT3, the wake of the natural terrain is not fully recovered.

A slight wake deflection can be seen in Figure 9, where the velocity deficit peaks at $2.5D^*$ do not agree with WT's transects, there is a deviation of the minimum velocity peaks to the east. This can be explained by the effect of a topographic depression in the south of the WF, where a high flow circulation is generated (Figure 8) leading to a larger westerly wind speed component (Table 7). This phenomenon can be also seen in Figure 10, where the natural terrain wake contribution of the western terrain depression is observed in the form of a wind speed deficit leading to an increase in the west wind component.

Figure 10: Velocity field (90 m AGL) without the influence of a WF (left) and accounting for the WF influence (right).

The locations to the south of the experimental WF would be the most affected by the wind speed and direction conditions, and the theoretical WTs considered in this study. The studied potential sites are located at above $10D^*$ to the south and there is height a.s.l. reduction above 100 m.

Figure 11: Wind speed and direction of some positions of the possible BWTs locations to the south of the experimental Alaiz's WF. The radius of the polar plots refers to the height AGL.

Some of the possible back WTs (BWT) locations at $10D^*$ suffer from large wind speed deficits

when considering the WF wakes. Figure 11 shows some of the most affected possible BWTs. The wind direction does not show a large deviation, whereas the wind speed is reduced by about 1 m/s at heights above 20 m AGL.

4. Conclusions

In the present work, the CT location around the Alaiz experimental WF was simulated and validated with experimental data. The effect of using $k - \varepsilon - f_P$ EVM in cases where WTs wakes are not modelled was compared with $k - \varepsilon$ EVM, which gave similar results in terms of wind speed, direction and TKE. This justified its suitability in the calculated cases shown in this work. The CT model was calibrated and validated in terms of wind speed and direction with the available met masts experimental data, showing a good agreement. The wake dissipation of a virtual WF setup with the theoretical NREL5MW WT in the available positions of the Alaiz experimental WF was studied as a function of terrain complexity.

The virtual WF contribution to the natural terrain deficit of velocities and the wakes dissipation was studied at different distances downwards, up to $75D^*$ (9450 m); in the different WTs transects. The WT1, WT4, WT5 and WT6 transects in CT showed a full wake recovery at $75D^*$. The slight WF wake deflection in CT was attributed to a topographic depression to the west of the WF, which increases the westerly wind component.

The methodology used covered only one wind speed and direction, with theoretical WTs. Consequently, the scope of the investigation was restricted to a particular wind condition, yielding a substantial amount of data for WRA. The theoretical effect of the WF layout on other possible WTs sites in the vicinity was investigated and showed that the theoretical WTs would lead to a reduction in wind speed of up to 1 m/s at the potential BWTs sites to the south of the experimental WF (at above $10D^*$).

Furthermore, higher fidelity computations (Large Eddy Simulations) with more reliable wake models (ALM) should be performed in future works to verify the conclusions of this study.

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